

Machine Learning-Based Plant Disease Detection Using Image Analysis

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Abstract—The research focuses on the design and construction of an image-based disease classification model based on deep learning techniques. The model aims to classify plants' leaves and stems into one of the five categories: black spots, downy mildew, powdery mildew, healthy, and other diseases. A dataset downloaded from a public sourced datasets and preprocessing techniques involving resizing, color normalization, and augmentation techniques, like rotation and flip, are used to enhance the model's efficiency. The deep model, built from the use of TensorFlow and the Keras API, performs image-based extraction of the images through the use of the convolution layer, enhancing the model's ability to distinguish between different health states in plants. Evaluation results show that the model achieves around 40% confidence when identifying one of the three diseases, indicating reasonable performance with room for future improvement. The model's efficiency in terms of classification measurement confirms the model's reliability in disease prediction. The current research identifies the use of deep models in the future in the field of agriculture to offer scalable and automatable means to disease prediction and monitoring in plants.

Keywords—Black spots, computer vision, downy mildew, feature extraction, Keras, plant disease, powdery mildew.

I. INTRODUCTION

THIS research offers an exhaustive methodology to build an image-based disease-classifying model for plants based on deep learning. Through the incorporation of advanced preprocessing techniques, the use of data augmentation techniques, and the use of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture, the model proposed in the paper is designed to classify different diseases in plants. The methodology begins by acquiring images from a public domain, and the images are standardized by resizing and normalizing them to the color model of Red, Green, Blue (RGB). RGB are the color channels in an image that make up a color for that pixel. Image augmentation techniques, including zoom, flip, and rotation, are applied to increase the size of the dataset and, in turn, the model's generalization and robustness. The model is later trained to classify unique patterns in the images to different diseases in plants.

Following preprocessing, the CNN architecture is constructed using a Keras model. This model comprises multiple convolutional layers for feature extraction, pooling layers for dimensionality reduction, and fully connected layers for final classification. Training the network involves compiling the model with the Adam optimizer, setting a carefully chosen loss function, and defining training parameters

such as epochs and batch size.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Plant diseases pose a major threat to global agriculture, leading to significant economic and food security challenges. Early detection is essential for mitigating losses, and recent advancements in machine learning have enabled more accurate identification of plant diseases through image classification. In 2021, Ristaino's research [2] highlights the severe impact of plant diseases on agriculture, with historical examples like the Irish Potato Famine caused by *Phytophthora infestans*. The study emphasizes the need for early detection methods and improved disease monitoring to prevent large-scale agricultural crises. Additionally, global food demand is projected to rise by 60% by the year 2050.

Plant diseases pose a significant threat to global food security by reducing crop yields, increasing processes, and exacerbating food scarcity. In Condoleo's paper, they discuss how agricultural diseases, including plant diseases, disrupt food systems and the broader food chain [1]. Additionally, in Ristaino et al.'s research, they emphasize the growing danger of plant disease pandemics, particularly those affecting crops, and underscore the importance of monitoring and managing plant health to ensure food stability worldwide [2]. The study by Wang outlines how emerging plant diseases are contributing to the global food security crisis [3]. Furthermore, Kreuze et al. highlight the role of technological advancements in understanding and combating plant virus diseases, which are critical in addressing food security challenges caused by plant health issues [4].

Image-based plant disease detection has become a critical tool in modern agriculture, leveraging digital imaging and machine learning techniques. In Khirade et al.'s research, they provides an overview of various image-processing methods for identifying plant diseases [5]. In Mohan et al.'s paper, they highlight the use of clustering and neural networks to improve plant disease classification, demonstrating the potential of machine learning for enhanced accuracy [6]. Also, in Khakimov et al.'s paper, they further discuss the evolution of plant disease detection methods, with an emphasis on how image-based techniques have become essential for the agricultural industry [7].

Machine learning, particularly through deep learning frameworks like Keras, plays a pivotal role in the classification of plant diseases. Benbrahim et al. demonstrate in their article

the application of CNNs in image classification with skin cancer, which is highly relevant for plant disease detection using Keras [8]. Lee and Jongwoo introduce CNNs with Keras, offering valuable insight for those applying deep learning to classification tasks [9]. Papers from Kissel et al [10] and Linse et al [11] both expand on the use of CNNs with pre-defined filters, which could help improve the classification accuracy of plant disease detection models.

Effective feature extraction is crucial to the accuracy of plant disease systems, as it directly impacts the model's ability to classify diseases correctly. Nguyen and Paik explore the use of triplet loss feature extraction, which can improve the precision of disease classification [12]. In a similar vein, Tekawade et al. introduce autoencoders for unsupervised feature extraction, offering techniques that could be adapted for plant disease detection [13]. Chen et al. provide valuable insight in their paper into using deep learning for feature extraction from hyperspectral data, which can be transferred to enhance plant disease detection models [14]. Bhargavi highlights the role of data augmentation in improving feature extraction and model accuracy, a key technique in enhancing the robustness of plant disease detection systems [15]. Finally, Rahmad et al. demonstrated the application of RGB image feature extraction methods like Gabor filters, which aligns well with the use of RGB images for feature extraction in plant disease

classification [16].

III. METHODOLOGY

This research involves several key stages to ensure accurate plant disease classification of the sample of plant diseases targeted by this model, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The process begins with the collection of images, which were sources from the public datasets provided by Jena [17] and Chauhan [18]. After collection, the images are preprocessed by resizing them to uniform dimensions and converting them to RGB format. Augmentation techniques such as flipping, rotation, and zooming are then applied to diversify the dataset, improving generalizability and counteracting overfitting. The dataset is divided into training and validation sets, followed by the construction of a CNN model in Keras. The model consists of multiple convolutional layers designed to extract meaningful features, with pooling and fully connected layers to facilitate classification. Training is conducted over several epochs, using backpropagation and optimization algorithms to refine model performance. Accuracy and loss metrics are continuously monitored to identify the optimal point for training. Once the model achieves satisfactory accuracy, it is saved for deployment, allowing users to input images for disease classification.

Fig. 1 Sample of plants with diseases

Fig. 1 presents samples of leaves affected by different diseases the model aims to recognize. Fig. 1 (a) depicts a leaf affected by downy mildew, a fungal disease typified by light green or yellow spots on the upper side, accompanied by white, fuzzy, or gray undergrowth. The disease thrives in cool, damp conditions and significantly compromises the health of the plant by inhibiting the function of photosynthesis. Fig. 1 (b) depicts a leaf affected by a pervasive fungal disease known as leaf

spots, typified by many tiny, dark spots scattered on the surface of the leaf. Over time, these spots may increase in size, and in some cases, lead to leaf drop, thereby weakening the plant. The model aims to recognize the unique patterns in the spots and distinguish them from other damage and discoloration. Fig. 1 (c) depicts a case of powdery mildew, another fungal disease marked by powdery, white deposits covering the surface of the leaves. Unlike the case of the downy mildew, the powdery

mildew usually targets plants in warm, dry locations. If left unattended, it inhibits the growth of plants and reduces crop yields. Through the examination of images such as the

examples presented, the model develops the skills to recognize the unique patterns in each disease, making accurate classification possible in the case of new plant images.

Fig. 2 A flowchart of how the model and website work

Once the model is trained, it can be used to classify new images uploaded by users. The flowchart shows that when a user submits an image, it undergoes feature extraction before being processed by the trained model. The predictive model then analyzes the extracted features and assigns a label indicating whether the plant is healthy or affected by a disease. This structured approach ensures that the model can effectively recognize patterns in plant images, making it a valuable tool for early disease detection and intervention.

A. Resizing and Color Filter

A fundamental preprocessing step in image-based machine learning involves resizing the input images and converting them to the RGB format. Both of these operations are essential for ensuring compatibility and consistency within the dataset. Resizing standardizes the dimensions of all images, which is critical when working with CNNs, as they require uniform input shapes. This process not only improves computational efficiency but also prevents errors that may arise from varying

image sizes.

The resizing process typically involves loading each image and scaling it to a fixed size, commonly 256 x 256 pixels. This ensures that all images share the same dimensions, making it easier for the network to process the data uniformly.

Equally important is the transformation of images into the RGB color space. RGB images use three color channels: red, green, and blue, which are commonly expected by most pre-trained models and standard CNN architectures. This conversion step is particularly necessary when working with images that are originally in grayscale or contain an alpha channel (i.e., four channels including transparency). By converting such images to the standard three-channel RGB, the preprocessing step preserves essential visual features, especially color-based cues. This is particularly important in applications such as plant disease detection, where subtle color variations can indicate different types of disease and significantly influence the accuracy of classification.

B. Augmentation

To enhance the model's generalization and avoid overfitting, image augmentation techniques are performed on the dataset. Augmentation introduces diversity in the training data artificially by incorporating transformations like flipping, rotation, and zooming. Flipping allows the model to identify disease patterns independent of orientation, and rotation makes

the model insensitive to varying viewing angles. Zooming slightly alters the size of an image so that the model can zoom in on various parts of a plant and get fine details. These operations enhance the model's capability to accurately classify plant diseases despite lighting, angle, or positional differences. Fig. 3 provides examples of augmented plant images, indicating how these transformations alter the dataset while preserving significant features for classification.

Fig. 3 Augmentation of the input images

Fig. 3 illustrates various augmentation techniques used to enhance the dataset and improve model generalization. Flip horizontal mirrors the image along the vertical axis, allowing the model to recognize plant diseases from different orientations. Flip vertical inverts the image along the horizontal axis, ensuring robustness to changes in perspective. Rotation alters the image's angle, simulating real-world scenarios where

plants may be viewed from different positions. Translation shifts the image slightly in different directions, helping the model learn to detect diseases even when the subject is not perfectly centered. These augmentations preserve key features while increasing data diversity, ultimately improving classification accuracy and model performance.

C. Convolutional Neural Network

A CNN acts as the core architecture employed by the image-based disease model to classify diseases in plants. The CNNs are programmed to automatically learn the hierarchical representations of image features at multiple layers through the operation of convolution. Through the use of the convolution layers, the essential patterns, such as color, texture, and edges, are found, and they represent possible disease signs in plants. The pooling layers later reduce the size of the feature maps, consequently reducing the network's computational

requirements while retaining the essential details. Towards the end of the network, fully connected layers examine the extracted features to classify images into particular diseases like the spots, the downy mildew, and the powdery mildew, and also evaluate the overall health status or other diseases. Through the use of various techniques at different layers to perform the extraction of the features, the use of CNNs ensures accurate disease determination. Additionally, the use of deep learning ensures the model's adaptability to images of different plants, making the model useful in real-life applications. The architecture of the model is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 The CNN

Fig. 4 shows the CNN architecture used for plant disease classification. The model is built sequentially, starting with a Convolutional 2D layer with 32 filters (of 3x3 blocks), which scans image regions to detect basic patterns like edges and textures. ReLU activation passes forward only meaningful features. A MaxPooling2D layer (of 2x2 block) follows to reduce spatial dimensions and computation. This pattern repeats with 64 and 128 filters in deeper convolutional layers, enabling the model to learn more complex features. After the final pooling layer, a Flatten layer converts 2D feature maps into a 1D vector. The model then includes two Dense layers (256 and 128 units), with ReLU activations to learn deeper patterns. A dropout layer helps prevent overfitting by randomly disabling up to half of the neurons during training. The output layer uses softmax activation to assign probabilities across the five plant disease classes. The model is compiled using the Adam optimizer and categorical cross-entropy loss, with accuracy as the performance metric. This architecture balances feature extraction, generalization, and classification, making it effective for plant disease detection from images.

D. Training

Training the model is essential for accurate plant disease classification. The dataset is split into training and validation sets, allowing the model to learn from most data while being tested on unseen examples. The CNN trains over multiple epochs, using backpropagation to update weights based on the loss function's gradients. The Adam optimizer is used for efficient weight adjustment, and the model minimizes the categorical cross-entropy loss to reduce the gap between predicted and actual labels. Performance is tracked using accuracy and loss metrics, helping detect underfitting or

overfitting. Dropout and data augmentation are used to improve generalization when overfitting is detected. The model is compiled with a learning rate of 0.0003, using Sparse Categorical Crossentropy and Sparse Categorical Accuracy as the evaluation metric.

Training is executed using the fit function, with 4 epochs and a batch size of 64. A callback is included to save the model at the end of each epoch, enabling recovery or continued training if needed. Validation data are provided to monitor generalization and prevent overfitting. These steps together ensure the CNN is trained efficiently to classify plant diseases from new images.

E. Accuracy

Accuracy is a key metric in evaluating the performance of the plant disease classification model. Fig. 5 shows the graph of accuracy and loss during training, along with a confusion matrix that is presented in Fig. 6. These images illustrate how well the model performs and how the accuracy improves over multiple epochs. A higher accuracy indicates that the model is making correct predictions more frequently, while a lower accuracy may suggest the need for further optimization, such as data augmentation or model adjustments. Once training is complete, the final accuracy score will reflect how well the model generalizes to new, unseen images.

In Fig. 5, the loss and accuracy graphs allow us to visualize the model's performance over time. They help track improvements in accuracy and identify periods where the model may have stagnated or faced challenges, guiding future adjustments and optimizations.

Fig. 5 The accuracy and loss from the model

Fig. 6 The confusion matrix after 4 epochs

Fig. 7 The prediction of a plant disease with Powdery Mildew after model training

Additionally, Fig. 6 presents a confusion matrix showing the model’s classification behavior, highlighting the true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives. This breakdown offers valuable insights into areas where the model might be making errors.

F. Result

The results of the model demonstrate its ability to classify plant diseases with varying confidence levels. The prediction image in Fig. 7 is an example of the model analyzing a leaf and determining its condition. In this case, the model predicts the presence of Powdery Mildew with a confidence of 40.46%. This suggests some uncertainty, indicating that the model also considers other potential classifications. While the model successfully identifies disease patterns, cases with lower confidence scores may require further refinement through additional training or dataset improvements.

Fig. 7 provides a detailed evaluation of the model’s

performance using key metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-score. It visually demonstrates the model's ability to distinguish between five classes: healthy, downy mildew, black spots, powdery mildew, and other diseases. The confusion matrix highlights both correct predictions and misclassifications, revealing patterns that indicate the model's strengths and weaknesses. Notably, a high number of misclassified cases occur between similar diseases, suggesting challenges for in distinguishing closely related symptoms.

IV. CONCLUSION

This research demonstrates the effective use of deep learning and image analysis to address agricultural challenges. By preprocessing plant images, employing feature extraction, and enhancing the dataset through augmentation, the system successfully classifies plant diseases such as black spots, downy mildew, and powdery mildew with an accuracy of around 40% confidence. The model's performance is tracked through accuracy and loss curves, where the accuracy initially dips before gradually improving and reaching a plateau, signaling the ideal stopping point for training. The robust design and performance of the model ensure it is suitable for real-world applications, allowing users to upload images and receive dependable predictions. The confusion matrix shows that there are improvements to be made showing that some images are being labeled wrong. Future improvements, including dataset expansion, hyperparameter optimization, and real-time analysis, are expected to further enhance the model's accuracy and usability, contributing to sustainable farming practices and improving crop health.

REFERENCES

- [1] Condoleo R. et al. "Livestock Health and Food Chain Risk Assessment." *EFSA Journal*, vol. 16, 2018.
- [2] Ristaino, Jean B., Pamela K. Anderson, Daniel P. Bebber, Kate A. Brauman, Nik J. Cunniffe, Nina V. Fedoroff, Cambria Finegold, et al. 2021. "The Persistent Threat of Emerging Plant Disease Pandemics to Global Food Security." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 118 (23). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2022239118>.
- [3] Yunpeng Gai, and Hongkai Wang. "Plant Disease: A Growing Threat to Global Food Security." *Agronomy*, vol. 14, no. 8, 2024, p. 1615. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy14081615>.
- [4] Kreuze, Jan F., et al. "New Technologies Provide Innovative Opportunities to Enhance Understanding of Major Virus Diseases Threatening Global Food Security." *Phytopathology*, vol. 113, no. 9, 2023, pp. 1622–29. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-12-22-0457-V>.
- [5] Khirade, Sachin D., A.B. Patil, and 2015 International Conference on Computing Communication Control and automation (ICCUBEA) Pune, India 2015 Feb. 26 - 2015 Feb. 27. 2015. "Plant Disease Detection Using Image Processing." In *2015 International Conference on Computing Communication Control and Automation*, 768–71. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCUBEA.2015.153>.
- [6] Mohan, Aditya, Kushagra Srivastava, Garima Malhotra, Nafis Uddin Khan, and 2020 Sixth International Conference on Parallel, Distributed and Grid Computing (PDGC) Wanknaghat, Solan, India 2020 Nov. 6 - 2020 Nov. 8. 2020. "Plant Disease Detection Using Clustering Based Segmentation and Neural Networks." In *2020 Sixth International Conference on Parallel, Distributed and Grid Computing (PDGC)*, 506–10. <https://doi.org/10.1109/PDGC50313.2020.9315856>.
- [7] Khakimov, A, I Salakhutdinov, A Omolikhov, and S Utaganov. n.d. "Traditional and Current-Prospicive Methods of Agricultural Plant Diseases Detection: A Review." *IOP Conference Series. Earth and Environmental Science* 951 (1): 12002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/951/1/012002>.
- [8] Benbrahim H., Hachimi H., and Amine A. 2020. "Deep Convolutional Neural Network with Tensorflow and Keras to Classify Skin Cancer Images." *Scalable Computing* 21 (3): 379–89. <https://doi.org/10.12694:/scpe.v21i3.1725>.
- [9] Lee, Hagyeong, and Jongwoo Song. 2019. "Introduction to Convolutional Neural Network Using Keras; an Understanding from a Statistician." *Communications for Statistical Applications and Methods = 한국통계학회논문집* 26 (6): 591–610.
- [10] Kissel, Matthias, Klaus Diepold, and 2022 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN) Padua, Italy 2022 July 18 - 2022 July 23. 2022. "Convolutional Neural Networks with Analytically Determined Filters." In *2022 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IJCNN55064.2022.9891906>.
- [11] Linse, Christoph, Erhardt Barth, Thomas Martinetz, and 2023 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN) Gold Coast, Australia 2023 June 18 - 2023 June 23. 2023. "Convolutional Neural Networks Do Work with Pre-Defined Filters." In *2023 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IJCNN54540.2023.10191449>.
- [12] Nguyen, Ty V., Incheon Paik, and 2020 11th International Conference on Awareness Science and Technology (iCAST) Qingdao, China 2020 Dec. 7 - 2020 Dec. 9. 2020. "Feature Extraction with Triplet Loss to Classify Disease on Leaf Data." In *2020 11th International Conference on Awareness Science and Technology (iCAST)*, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/iCAST51195.2020.9319494>.
- [13] Tekawade, Aniket, Zhengchun Liu, Peter Kenesei, Tekin Bicer, Francesco De Carlo, Rajkumar Kettimuthu, Ian Foster, and 2021 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP) Anchorage, AK, USA 2021 Sept. 19 - 2021 Sept. 22. 2021. "3d Autoencoders for Feature Extraction in X-Ray Tomography." In *2021 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, 3477–81. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIP42928.2021.9506494>.
- [14] Chen, Yushi, et al. "Deep Feature Extraction and Classification of Hyperspectral Images Based on Convolutional Neural Networks." *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 54, no. 10, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2016.2584107>.
- [15] Bhargavi, T, D Sumathi, and 2023 5th International Conference on Smart Systems and Inventive Technology (ICSSIT) Tirunelveli, India 2023 Jan. 23 - 2023 Jan. 25. 2023. "Significance of Data Augmentation in Identifying Plant Diseases Using Deep Learning." In *2023 5th International Conference on Smart Systems and Inventive Technology (ICSSIT)*, 1099–1103. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSSIT55814.2023.10061007>.
- [16] Rahmad, C., et al. "Identification of Sugarcane Maturity Scale Based on RGB, Gabor Feature Extraction and Support Vector Machine." *IOP Conference Series. Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 434, no. 1, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/434/1/012065>.
- [17] Ashish Jena. Lettuce Diseases, April 17, 2024. V1. <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/ashishjstar/lettuce-diseases>
- [18] Chirag Chauhan. April 18, 2024. Rose Leaves Disease Detect, V1. <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/warcoder/rose-leaves-disease-detection>